

Religious Politicisation and Ethnicity as Steeplechases to National Integration in Nigeria

Samuel Anger Gbinde

*PG Student, Department of Religion and Cultural Studies,
Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria
samgbinde@gmail.com*

Abstract

Religion, politics and ethnicity in Nigeria are deeply rooted every facet of Nigerian life and have threatened the very survival of the nation. Religion which has been politicised is fertilised by ethnicity which in turn has negatively impacted on the socio-economic and bureaucratic landscape of Nigeria to the extent that issues that should have been resolved are unnecessarily ethicised or take a religious-political standpoint. This hydra headed quandary has persistently shown that the grievances which usually provoke religious, political and ethnic mendacities are most often than not demonstrated through sectarian crises, tribal unrests, and bitter political grumbles operated by political elites, incendiary media rhetoric reports and violent insurgencies and banditry. This paper argues that religious politicisation and ethnicity as steeplechases to national integration in Nigeria has arrested good governance and enthroned incompetence on the Nigerian socio-economic and political space. There have been religious and ethnic minorities that harbour grievances against the majorities' lack of inclusivity in Nigeria. Therefore, this paper bearing in mind the current events unfolding in the country, takes the onus of an academic perusal on the issue in order to proffer an enduring panacea to checkmate the disintegration that may be invoked by religious-political and ethnic palaver.

Keywords: Religious, Politicisation, Ethnicity, National Integration

Introduction

Nigeria as a nation from all indications has not attained her set targets of unifying the diverse ethnic groups in virtually all facets-socially, economically, politically among others since independence in 1960. A major contributing factor to this reality could be attributed to apparent lack of unity occasioned by religion, politics and ethnic dichotomy. Ethnic politics started during colonial era and it has had cumulative effects on the third and fourth republics. According to Jacob Ayantayo, in the first Republic, the Action Group (AG) as a party metamorphosed from a Yoruba Cultural Association-Egbe Omo Oduduwa; the National Council of Nigeria Citizens (NCNC) intimately linked with the Igbo Union and Northern Peoples' Congress (NPC) was an offshoot of Jamiyyar Arewa. The leadership of these parties were drawn along ethnic cleavages with their ethnic colourations. The Action Congress (A.G) was led by late Chief Obafemi Awolowo, a Yoruba and a Christian; the NCNC was headed by late Dr. Nnamdi Azikwe; an Igbo, also a Christian while the NPC was co-ordinated and led by Sir Ahmadu Bello, the Sardauna of Sokoto, a Fulani and a Muslim.

All these were products of the colonial administrative arrangement that propelled ethnic politics in that it divided Nigeria into three regions for effective administration; that is, West–Yoruba, North – Hausa/Fulani and East–Igbo. This division reflects the three major ethnic groups in the country. It is worthy of note that in addition to issue of ethnicity is the religious question which is becoming endemic and volatile, intruding into the political sphere of the country. Islam, being theocentric in its doctrine, opposes secularity which is constitutionally allowed in religiously pluralistic societies like Nigeria, has threatened the stability and development of the nation with a claim to numerical superiority.¹

There is a strong correlation between religious differences, ethnic and regional diversity. The north, dominated by the large Hausa and Fulani ethnic groups, is predominantly Muslim with significant numbers of Christians. Both Muslims and Christians are found in large numbers in the Middle Belt. In the southwest, where the large Yoruba ethnic group is the majority, there is no dominant religion. Most Yorubas practice either

Christianity or Islam, while others continue to practice the traditional Yoruba religion, which includes a belief in a supreme deity and the worship of lesser deities that serve as the supreme deity's agents in aspects of daily life. In the east, where the large Igbo ethnic group is dominant, Catholics, Anglicans, and Methodists are the majority, although many Igbos continue to observe traditional rites and ceremonies in tandem with Christianity. Religious differences often mirror regional and ethnic differences. For example, persons in the North and in parts of the Middle Belt are overwhelmingly Muslim and from the large Hausa and Fulani ethnic groups that tend to dominate these areas. Many southern ethnic groups are predominantly Christians. In many areas of the Middle Belt, Muslim Fulani tend to be pastoralists, while the Muslim Hausa and most Christian ethnic groups tend to be farmers or work in urban areas. Consequently, ethnic, regional, economic, and land use competition often coincide with religious differences between the competing groups.²

Conceptual Clarification Religion

Religion and politics are concepts that have been subjected to different definitions from various scholars of repute. As such, there seems to be no straight jacketed definitions of the concepts. Religion is an important aspect of life; it influences many great things. Religion is a belief system that uses symbols to allow people to explore their spirituality.³ Religions, many at times depend on symbols and narratives usually employed to offer a meaning to human existence and also to explain the indices for the creation of the universe. In addition, there are some religions that have ethical foundations indicating how their adherents should behave in any given society. This could have led Olufemi Oluniyi to rightly observe that “religion is a source and guarantor of individual and societal peace.”⁴

It is expedient to state that one aspect of religion that is applicable in all instances is that it is a public process. The basic requirement is that the religion being a belief system must be held by a group of people who publicly share its doctrine. Religious beliefs are evident in religious dogma, creed, conviction, doctrine and principles. Therefore, religious practices encompass different religious activities such as worship, fellowship, communion, prayer, offering and almsgiving and so on. Olumide Adesina is of the opinion that religious ethics are the moral principles that guide religions and set the standard for what is and isn't acceptable behaviour from all indications, religious ethics covers every aspect of man's life. It is revelational, decision oriented, scriptural; traditional, legalistic and life directed.⁵

Politics

From a common view, “Politics is who gets what, when and how.”⁶ Using the Nigerian political experience, the political class have been using various means including religion and ethnicity to hold on to power. Politics has therefore been used for the promotion of self-aggrandisement in the name of who gets what, when and how? Porta, Donatella Della sees politics as having to do with efficient organisation and judicious administration of the collective affairs of the organised human community.⁷ This however was the conception of ancient philosophers such as Plato (470:399BC), (354 – 322BC) about politics. Both thought of it in moderate and idealistic terminologies, as having to do with fashioning a structurally and functionally perfect human community that would be motivated at all times by the quest to promote justice and happiness for her citizens.⁸ These early views emphasized what politics ought to be rather than what it actually is.

Furthermore, politics is the science or the art of the management of public affairs.⁹ In the contemporary period, a breed of people called politicians have emerged who claim to have the necessary qualifications for the efficient management of public affairs except in totalitarian state where sectarian views and ideas are regimental or forcibly suppressed. These politicians in addition, naturally form themselves into groups called parties each with different ideas of its own and divergent methods of realizing those ideas. David Kolawole is of the view that that in a democratic society, citizens entrust their representatives with the management of affairs by voting in

candidates of their political choice. This therefore connotes that for national integration to be attained, politics must be fairly played to accommodate the verdict of the electorates.¹⁰

Obafemi Awolowo contends that for politics to engender national integration, the popular misconceptions of ‘Politics, ethnicity and Religion do not mix’ should be erased. Awolowo contends that “politics is essentially materialistic and religion is so fundamentally spiritual”. Therefore, it may be difficult for a man to be a successful politician and good Christian or Muslim at the same time.¹¹ In actualising the integrative effort of man in ensuring national development, the agencies of politics and religion must work in close and harmonious collaboration. This is only attainable in a situation where politics without bitterness is played. It can be argued that politics and religion that could have been forces promoting national integration have failed completely in achieving same as shall be seen shortly.

Religious Politicisation

Politicisation, on the other hand, is a term used to explain how ideas, entities, or body of facts acquire a political tone or character and are consequently associated with the ideas and strategies of a particular group or party, and thus become the subject of argument. According to José Casanova, politicisation is narrowly defined here as the rise of a successful religious party in the national political field. While many political actors and organizations claim to represent the interests of religious groups and want to establish successful religious parties, these religio-political projects often fail.¹² Politicisation of religion is a term developed as the effect of religion, dealing with mixing materials in religion with political matters. Jürgen Habermas states that religion takes a more role in politics. In fact, religion issues lead people in deciding their political action in presidential election and regional selection, law legalisation and local regulation, even in state constitution.

National Integration

Integration, which literally means assembling parts into a whole, has been defined variously.¹³ The one employed depends on the observer’s perception of what constitutes national integration and the strategy for achieving social stability and social progress. National integration refers to the process of bringing diverse cultural and social groups into a single territorial unit and the establishment of a national unity.¹⁴ The term presumes the existence of an ethnically plural society in which each group is characterized by its own language, or other self-conscious cultural qualities, which generate the problem of creating a sense of territorial nationality, which overshadows or eliminates subordinate parochial loyalties. Olaleye Adebayo Olufemi defined integration as a progressive removal of antagonisms and reduction of cultural and regional decisions and differences in the process of creating a homogenous political unit.¹⁵

From the foregoing, national integration refers to the process of building a just social units which confers on every inhabitant within it a sense of belonging, a satisfactory level of participation in decision-making and development and a change to share from the resources of the society commensurate with decent and acceptable living.

Ethnicity as Steeplechases to National Integration in Nigeria

Nigeria party politics has been characterised by ethnic chauvinism. This is one of the major challenges confronting the advancement of liberal democracy in Nigeria since independence. To the extent that ethnic sentiment is fully introduced in virtually all areas of Nigerian political system. Indeed, low productivity and inefficiencies currently experienced in the country can be attributed to ethnic sentiment. Based on lingual classification, Nigeria is said to have about 250 ethnic groups. A federal government demographic survey in 1976 identified 394 language groups, one put it as high as 400 with the highest density of languages in Taraba and Adamawa States. This therefore suggests that Nigeria is multi-lingual and multi-ethnic in nature. These tribal differences have given room for diverse nature of the Nigerian State. Hence, the paradox “unity-in-diversity”. This further indicates that though housed in one country, the ethnic groups do not have identical needs, objectives

and aspirations. Ethnic politics has become a formidable force in the political life of Nigeria. Most often, ethnic sentiments are used in place of merit and skills.

For instance, in the case of appointment, round pegs are no longer found in round holes. Ethnicity has been one of the major factors that have seriously dampened the image and glory of Nigerian party politics. The first evident to justify this is the adoption and practice of federal character principle. The “federal character” principle, which has been enshrined in Nigeria constitution since 1979, seeks to ensure that appointments to public service institutions fairly reflect the linguistic, ethnic, religion and geographic diversity of the country.¹⁶

It follows clearly that federal character is a tool for ensuring fairness in public service over professionalism and goal attainment. The total systemic collapse in Nigeria’s socio-economic and political environment can be attributed to the federal character practice.¹⁷ The imbalance in the literacy rate between the South and the North of Nigeria has made it impossible to have qualified people in sensitive government positions. For example, the North would rather let an Arabic “Alamijiri” teacher from the north to be the minister of education, than allow a southerner to play the role, all because of a perceived need for proper representation in the name of federal character principle which has been ethnicised.

It is observed that parties now adopt the principles of federal character as a means of gaining credibility which goes along with religious and ethnic colourations.

Still within the purview of federal character which has been negatively affected by ethnic politics is the fact that merit has not been achieved at the altar of federal character principle, Korieh Chima and Nwokeji argues that, “for one, there is always a minimum requirement for appointment into any post within the federal civil service, Armed Forces, the police any other agency of government. I never heard of any situation where minimum requirement for any particular post was dependent upon the candidate’s ethnic, religious, geopolitical or state circumstances.”

However, due to the influx of religious and ethnic colourations into the principle, it has accelerated the promotion of incompetent and ineffective civil servants, military, paramilitary officers, even top government functionaries. The inappropriate application of federal character creates mediocrity, inequality, corruption, lack of transparency and above all tribal dominance by the major ethnic groups. Besides, to indicate the extent to which ethnic politics has adversely impacted on national integration, the leading ethnic groups have exploited the available constitutional provision to their benefits in the areas of contract award, infrastructural development and appointment into strategic government institutions. Such actions create a few rich and powerful individuals; increase poverty, ensures uneven regional development and high incidence of grotto.

The former minister of Science and Technology, Gen. Sani Momah (Rtd) opined that “federal character as it is currently practised in Nigeria tends to inculcate cheating rather than emphasise hardwork, selflessness and nation-building, the core values which our founding fathers lived by”.¹⁹ The demand and desperation for the creation of states and local governments in the country have been informed by ethnic sentiments and marginalisation. For example, the Idoma which is a minority ethnic group in Benue State has been complaining of marginalisation by Tiv which is the majority ethnic group in the state. It is apparent that Tiv have been producing civilian executive governors notably, Chief Aper Aku, in the first republic, Moses Orshio Adasu in the third republic, George Akume, in fourth republic and now Gabriel Suswan and Samuel Ortom in the fifth republic. The Idoma now feels that the only solution is the creation of “Apa State.”²⁰ This is just a case out of many calls by the minority ethnic groups of neglect and marginalisation stoked by ethnic politics. The impacts of ethnic politics could also be noticed in the area of the allocation of national resources.

Besides, ethnic politics has had effect on the Nigerian polity because it heightens political struggle and competition in electoral contest. This is well substantiated for using the activities of the Northern Peoples’ Congress (NPC) in the First Republics when the north insisted that its candidates must win at all cost, to actualise this, some northern candidates were returned unopposed even before the commencement of the general elections. It is obvious that the current political impasse in which case the north is making frantic efforts to install any candidates from the region points to the impact of religion and ethnic politics in Nigeria. Even the result of general

elections conducted in 1993 between Social Democratic Party SDP and National Republic Convention NRC was annulled based on some factors among which ethnic politics was one, Abiola was then precluded from becoming the executive president in Nigeria. In fact, the election was well rated to have been very free and fair both in conduct and organisation.

Religious Politicisation as Steeplechase to National Integration in Nigeria

Nigeria is a country blessed with a triple religious heritage. Her religious landscape has been dominated by three major religious groups. The adherents of the traditional religion, the Muslims and Christians. Indeed, by the period of Nigeria's independence in 1960, the country was divided along religious zones of influence, notably, the largely Muslim North and the Christian south. The latter was later split into the predominantly catholic east and the west having the same numerical strength of Muslims and Christians.²¹ The traditional religion as mentioned elsewhere in the study, appears to be un-proselytised religion because it does go forth seeking converts neither does it pick offense when deserted by its adherents nor assume that its object of worship is superior. It has the rare quality of accommodation and tolerance to other religions.²²

It must be argued that the politicisation of religion has contributed adversely to the disintegration of Nigeria. The first justification for this assertion can be attributed to the regime of Babangida when Nigeria became a member of the Organisation of Islamic Conference (OIC). Although Babangida government claimed to have taken the decision for economic reasons: to be able to access the loans available to OIC member countries at a time Nigeria was direly in need of finance. Christians, however, viewed this as an attempt to Islamise Nigeria. This of course was the beginning of Christian Versus Muslim open confrontation in Nigeria.

This paper finds out that the first major religions riot occasioned by ethnic politics was the one that pitched Muslims and Christians against each other in Kafanchan, old Kaduna State in March 1987. The following month, the usually peaceful Ilorin, Kwara State, also witnessed a skirmish when some exuberant Christian youths held an Easter procession in a thickly Muslim neighbourhood, pointing at houses and singing: "Jesus dey here? "He dey...!"²³ The tension went on and on, with Zaria, Tafawa Balewa, Zango Kotaf, Kano and the recent killing of Miss Deborah Samuel in Sokoto State.

Another area where it is discovered that religious politics has devastated the integrative efforts of Nigeria could be found when the embattled former Central Bank Governor Mallam Sanusi Lamido Sanusi was suspended due to financial misconduct and replaced by Godwin Emefiele, a Christian, who was yet to assume office as at the period of this study. Only for some groups in the North to start using ethno-religious justification for the removal of Sanusi Nairaland Forum 23rd Monday, 2014. The president of the senate, Senator David Mark raised the alarm over the antics of some desperate persons using politics and religion to destroy the unity and peace of the Nigerian nation. David Mark Warned "To sponsor or promote violence, destruction and uncharitable utterances in the name of politics or religion is totally unacceptable and must be condemned in the strongest terms...the current and political confusion are avoidable distraction we certainly do not need now".²⁴ He concluded by saying he observed that most people tend to use politics and religion for the wrong reasons, stating "what we need now is to embark on serious political and inter-religious dialogue with the spirit of frankness, honesty, openness, acceptance and understanding in order to move forward."²⁵

Besides, religious politics had been used in the past to undermine the unity and the integrative efforts of Nigeria. Sheikh Abubakar in October 1987 could be used to sustain this postulation. He said: "The two-party system of government will not be south against North but Islam against Christianity. Once you are a Moslem, you cannot accept to choose a non-Moslem to be your leader. If Christians do not accept Moslems as their leader, then we have to divide the country. Nigerian unity is to try to convert Christians and non-Moslems (to Islam) until other religion become minority and they will not affect our society".²⁶

Due to religious politics, Nigeria is becoming field for suicide bombers. We are becoming another Iraq and Afghanistan. Today it is bomb-blast, tomorrow, it is people are killed in Maiduguri, bomb factory is discovered in Yobe, etc..²⁷ Moving further, the national integration of Nigeria as country is already being

impaired. This is justifiable with the Muslim's call for autonomy flies in the face of Nigeria's secular tradition. The constitution does not at all elevate any religion to a state religion. Yet, this principle was violated when governors in the Northern state issued authority to Islamize public life. In Zamfara, the first state to introduce a strict form of Sharia, the government claimed that its religious reform was bringing about major changes, whereas all spheres of public life were being transformed into Islamic oriented institutions. This state-sponsored Islamisation affected non-Muslims as well, they were subjected to some sharia proscriptions like the ban on alcohol and the gender separation in hotels and restaurants, in buses and taxis. All these have adversely hampered national integration of Nigeria even in terms of economic development. Because foreign investors might not be interested to site their industries in a crisis ridden country. The tendency of religious groups to politicise religious activities has made the country more difficult to govern. In some sects, political matters are viewed with the spectacle of religious, appeal to religious sentiment as a potent weapon which invariably makes the integration of Nigeria to be in shamble.

Another adverse effect religious politics has had on the country's integration is the promotion of culture of corruption. Virtually every aspect of society is corrupt and religion that should have been a tool of correction has failed in this regard. Majority of the Pastors and Imams have aided and abetted corruption in that their followers have been tasked to look for money at all cost 'to help God'. Whereas, the Holy books (both the Bible and Quran) have not taught them that. The effect of the foregoing is that religious ideals is expected to regulate the political activities. However, majority of political office holders who would have impacted positively on the national integration given the genuine teachings by their religious leaders have failed to do so because the truth has not been preached. Religious politics has nevertheless precipitated various religious conflicts.

Arguments were generated among the members of National Delegates National Conference of the then President Goodluck Jonathan over the dominance of one religious sect. On 1st April, 2014 as indicated in the Nigerian newspapers especially *The Punch* where the adherents of the two religions engaged in debate over the dominance of Islam in the 1999 constitution without any mention of Christianity. As the two delegates representing Christianity namely Bishop Kafanchan Diocese of Catholic Church, Joseph Bagobiri and Pastor Emmanuel Bosun (Ogun State) raised the issue which they described as unfair treatment of Christians and Christianity in the country. This of course angered their Muslim Counterparts who opposed their submissions.²⁸

Pastor Emmanuel Bosun argued that the conference must address religious imbalance in the country. He argued emphatically thus: "in the 1999 constitution, shariah was mentioned 73 times, Grand Khadi 54 times, Islam 28 times, Muslim 10 times and there is no single mention of Christ, Christian, Christianity or church. So, what are Christians doing here, 100 of our churches were burnt down, Christians are being killed. In fact, it has reached the stage of genocide".²⁹ Pastor Emmanuel Bosun substantiated his argument further by citing a particular example of Plateau State: "in one denomination in Plateau State, the women's Fellowship as at 2001 had 500 registered widows whose husbands had been killed by religious sect during riots. By 2008 they had increased to 900 registered widows and by February 2014, they had reached 2500 registered windows."³⁰

Conclusion

Ethnic politics and religion have impacted negatively on the development of the nation in many fronts namely socially, politically, economically and bureaucratically. It is a cancer requiring attention and sincere commitment with sacrifice from all Nigerians. In order to proffer lasting solution that brings about peace and engender proper national integration, the opinion of leaders vis-a-vis religions and political leaders must begin to emphasise the need to embrace peace at all cost. As the country remains multi-religions and ethno-linguistic pluralism, secularity is the best option that can uphold peace and harmony. It is possible that if Nigeria was not colonized, the entrenchment of ethnic sentiment among the different ethnic groups would have been very impossible. The federal government should strongly discourage the spirit of indigene-settler phenomenon in the country. Federal character principle must be strictly implemented both at the state and local levels of government. Fanaticism in religion must be de-emphasised in order to pave way for re-designing Nigerian Society.

In order to achieve national integration, therefore, not only must the government reel out fantastic policies and programmes, it must begin to build enduring institutions bigger and more powerful than the leadership. The leadership must become more accountable to the people and those members of the ruling class who fan the embers of hate, exploitation, ethnicity, marginalization and underdevelopment must be made to face the full wrath of the law. Corruption which has become endemic must be fought until it is either eradicated or forcibly punished so that those who engage in it do so at their own risk. Mass mobilization of the hoi polloi is necessary to reorient them with the right values consistent with a modern and emerging economy. Nigeria's diversity is not the problem, the managers of the state are. Nigerians must arise from the ashes of fear, wrongly inspired awe for political leaders and timidity and begin to make demands on the political leadership on what they want. For instance, the fuel subsidy strike of January 2012 sent and the recent #EndSARS protest in Lagos an eruptive message to the ruling class that the people would no longer sit idly and watch them ride the country aground. The time to question the disingenuousness of Nigeria and to demand for a tinkering of this gargantuan political edifice in line with the expectations of the Nigerian people is now.

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